

Task Proposal: EmotivITA, dimensional emotion regression with the EMOITA dataset

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Task description

EmotivITA is a task of emotion regression based on EMOITA, the Italian version of the EMOBANK dataset (Buechel and Hahn, 2017). Translation and annotation of the original *corpus* have been realised by a group of researchers at the Urban/Eco Interdepartmental Research Center of the University 'Federico II' of Naples and at the Humanities Department of the University of Catania.

We propose four tasks, both constraint and unconstraint ones:

- a1) Dimensional emotion regression: prediction of the Valence, Arousal and Dominance values based on a set of Italian sentences and annotations, using only the target annotated dimension for training.
- a2) Same as a1, using the original English annotations from the EmoBank *corpus*.
- b1) Multi-dimensional emotion regression: prediction of the Valence, Arousal and Dominance values based on a set of Italian sentences and annotations, using all of the annotated dimensions for prediction (so to exploit possible correlations within the different dimensions).
- b2) Same as b1, using the original English annotations from the EmoBank *corpus*.

In proposing these tasks, we aim to promote dimensional emotion analysis, a problem who has received increasing attention within the field of sentiment analysis in the English-speaking community, but not yet so among the Italian speakers.

Related works and international relevance of the task

In the past few years, affective computing has become a prominent area in Natural Language Processing. While early studies focused on predicting the semantic polarity (sentiment analysis) of a text (Basile et al, 2014), due to the astounding progresses of machine learning, research moved towards more fine-grained modelling of affective states. To make just a few examples in EVALITA recent history: aspect-based sentiment analysis, which aims to detect polarity classes in relation to multiple aspects of an opinion item (Basile et al.,

2018); automatic classification of specific communicative intentions, such as irony and sarcasm (Cignarella et al., 2018); stance detection, expected to determine the orientation of a writer in favour or against certain topics of interest (Cignarella et al, 2020).

So far, emotion analysis of Italian texts has not received the same amount of attention as sentiment analysis. Using an influential affective state taxonomy from Scherer (2000), we define emotion as a “relative brief episode of response to the evaluation of an external or internal event as being of major significance”, whereas sentiment corresponds to Scherer’s “attitude”: “relatively enduring, affectively colored beliefs, preferences, and predispositions toward objects or persons”.

What is true for emotion analysis is even truer about emotion dimensional analysis, which is based on dimensional models of emotions rather than categorical ones. While the latter describe affective states with limited sets of discrete emotions, such as those defined by Ekman or Plutchik, the former make use of a continuous scale spanning through three independent dimensions: Valence (degree of pleasure), Arousal (degree of excitement) and Dominance (degree of control over the situation).

The VAD model has received increasing attention in NLP tasks in English. Nevertheless, while a limited number of Italian *corpora* annotated with categorical models are available, to the best of our knowledge, no VAD annotated dataset exists for the Italian language.

With EMOTA we propose the first *corpus* of Italian sentences annotated with their VAD values. EMOTA is the Italian version of EMOBANK, the largest English VAD dataset to date. Sentences from EMOBANK have been first automatically translated in Italian, then manually revised and corrected by a group of Italian researchers affiliated with Urban/Eco. The same researchers also annotated each sentence with new VAD values.

To the best of our knowledge, state-of-the-art results for the EMOBANK *corpus* (English sentences, annotations based on a weighted average of reader and writer perspectives) has been obtained by Park et al. (2021). They claim they reached a *Pearson’s r* of 0.838 for Valence, of 0.573 for Arousal and of 0.536 for Dominance.

No studies do exist on the Italian *corpus*, except for a master dissertation by Giovanni Gafà, who reached a *Pearson’s r* of 0.793, 0.588, and 0.435 for Valence, Arousal and Dominance respectively, fine-tuning different BERT models with the Italian sentences and the English annotations, and a *Pearson’s r* of 0.591, 0.479 and 0.457 using Italian sentences and annotations.

With the proposal of these tasks, we intend to promote dimensional emotion analysis in Italian language, and to encourage a comparison with the English counterpart; the multidimensional subtasks, moreover, have the purpose of evaluating the possibility of a correlation between the three dimensions of the model, which has been discussed but never proved in literature.

Description and examples of the data, including information about their availability, development stage, and issues concerning privacy and data sensitivity.

For the task at hand, we will provide a development set of 8.000 Italian sentences with ID’s and two sets of annotations: the ones from the original EMOBANK corpus, resulting from a weighted average of the reader

and writer perspective on the sentences, and the ones annotated by the Italian researchers from just the reader perspective. The test set (2.063 sentences) will be released on the xx/xx/xx.

Valence, Arousal and Dominance are presented in a continuous scale from 1 to 5.

Example:

id	text	V eng	A eng	D eng	V ita	A ita	D ita
0001	Sono davvero stanco di te!	2.12	4.23	2.1	2.0	4.5	2.5

References

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